

WP2 – Optimising agroforestry design and management: tools for practitioners and farm advisors

Deliverable 2.3: Roadmap 1.0 on anticipated benefits and costs of agroforestry innovations

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1 Context

The DigitAF research project (July 2022 - June 2026), funded by the European Commission, aims for a high quality implementation of agroforestry to foster climate change mitigation and adaptation in agriculture and to ensure sustainable management of natural resources. Our goal is to provide the main actor groups with tools answering their needs, in particular digital tools. The three actors' groups that are the target for DigitAF are:

- Policy actors: policymakers and administrations concerned with applying agroforestry -related regulations, at regional, national and European levels, who set the scene for the adoption (or not) of agroforestry.
- Practitioners: farmers, landowners and by extension, farm advisers playing an active role in designing and managing AFS and whose choices determine the agronomic, economic, environmental, and social performance at farm-level and beyond.
- Beneficiaries of AF products and services: stakeholders in the value chain, including wholesalers, retailers, organisations trading the carbon sequestration and biodiversity benefits of AFS, and final consumers seeking verification of the benefits of AF in clear and accessible terms.

This report addresses Task 2.1 of the DigitAF project. Task 2.1 aims to better understand and optimise the technical, administrative, and financial aspects of installing and managing agroforestry in a farming landscape. In this report, we deal particularly with the financial aspects at farm level, which aims to enhance the quantification of the benefits and costs of selected agroforestry practices, relative to selected baseline enterprises. The DigitAF Living Labs are used as case studies.

Within work-package 4 of the DigitAF project, "Living Labs" were created in six countries across Europe: Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, Finland, Czechia, and the United Kingdom. Living labs have been defined as "user-centred, open innovation ecosystems based on a systematic user co-creation approach, integrating research and innovation processes in real life communities and settings" (Malmberg et al., 2017). Creating the Living Labs was the first step into the co-creation and collaboration process with representative stakeholders from the value chain of agroforestry products. Since then, we have been in continuous communication with the Living Lab participants in each country, consulting with them whenever needed, have used their expertise to progress each step of the project, and have considered their opinions and feedback in the development of the project deliverables and forward plan.

For each of the six Living Labs, this report contains the financial data for the agroforestry innovations for the same farms studied in Milestone 8 (economic performance of the baseline situation). This report presents "D2.3: Roadmap 1.0 on anticipated benefits and costs of agroforestry innovations" and will also provide the foundation for a future deliverable "D2.4: Roadmap 2.0 on anticipated benefits and costs of agroforestry innovations" to be produced in August 2025, in which the anticipated benefits and costs of incorporating agroforestry on farm will be assessed.

2 Methodology

Within this component of the DigitAF project, we are seeking to better understand and optimise the financial aspects of installing and managing agroforestry within existing farm businesses. The process of completing financial analysis of agroforestry innovations is primarily a five-stage process:

- 1) Selection of the case study farms,
- 2) Collection of biophysical and financial data of the baseline farm system,
- 3) Definition of the agroforestry innovation
- 4) Collection of biophysical and financial data on the agroforestry innovation,
- 5) The selection and development and use of financial models
- 6) The comparison of the benefits and costs of the agroforestry innovation relative to the baseline system.

These sections are briefly described in turn.

2.1 Selection of case study farms

Six case study farms, each linked to a Living Lab, have been selected for financial analysis. The case study farms are situated in Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, Finland, Czechia, and the United Kingdom (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Map showing location and spread of the Living Labs within Europe. The orange pins indicate central location to each of the Living Labs.

2.2 Collection of biophysical and financial data of the baseline farm system

The financial data for six baseline systems was described in a report entitled: “Milestone 8: Baseline System and the Associated Financial Benefits and Costs” produced on 27 June 2023 (Cumplido-Marin et al., 2023). That report provided an overview of the characteristics of the six Living Labs in the DigitAF project. The baseline systems include arable systems in Italy, Finland, the United Kingdom (UK), mixed farming in Germany and Czechia, and a livestock system in the Netherlands (Table 1). Please note that the costs for the systems for the Netherlands, Finland, and the UK in Table 1 have been updated from Milestone 8.

Table 1. Summary of results from the financial analysis in the participating countries (weighted mean). All values in € ha⁻¹ unless indicated.

Country	Italy	Germany	Nether-lands	Finland	Czechia	UK
Farming system	Arable	Mixed	Livestock	Arable	Mixed	Arable
Area (ha)	40	75	72	75	50	181
Mean crop yield (t ha ⁻¹)	2.4	-	na	1.4	-	4.0
Mean price (€ t ⁻¹)	201	-	na	165	-	306
Product revenue	518	1,468	7,718	346	209	1,271
Subsidies	264	136	381	749	555	242
Revenue	782	1,604	8,099	1,095	764	1,513
Variable costs	327	1136	4039	43	77	314
Assignable fixed costs	561	581	2481	160	883	270
Other fixed costs	-	-	155	-	-	-
Total costs	888	1,717	6,274	310	960	874
Gross margin with subsidies	455	468	4,060	1,052	687	953
Gross margin without subsidies	191	332	3,679	303	132	711
Net margin ^a with subsidies	-106	-113	1,980	785	-196	640
Net margin ^a without subsidies	-370	-249	1,599	36	-752	398

na = not applicable;

^a: Net margin based on gross margin minus assignable fixed costs

When modelling the economics of arable or livestock enterprises, it is generally common practice to undertake this on an annual basis using “gross margins” determined as the difference between the revenue (R ; units: € ha⁻¹) and variable costs (V ; units: € ha⁻¹) (Equation 1). On an arable farm, variable costs include the costs of seed, fertiliser, and sprays.

$$\text{Gross margin} = R - V$$

Equation 1

In a gross margin comparison, labour and machinery costs are typically not included as they can be considered to be “fixed” on annual basis. However, financial comparisons of baseline and agroforestry systems need to consider more than an annual period, because it takes several years for trees to achieve their potential yields. Hence comparisons of baseline and agroforestry systems typically are made on the basis of “net margins” which account for labour and machinery costs over time. Costs that are used to determine the net margin analysis in this way are termed “assignable fixed costs” (A ; units: € ha⁻¹) (Equation 2).

$$\text{Net margin} = R - V - A$$

Equation 2

2.3 Definition of the agroforestry innovation

During 2023, each of the six Living Labs have identified an agroforestry innovation that could form the focus of a financial analysis. A summary of those innovations are provided in Table 2.

Table 2. Summary of selected agroforestry innovations being examined within the six living labs.

Case study	Baseline system	Agroforestry Innovation
Enrico Avanzi Research Centre, Italy	Mixed crop rotation	Silvoarable agroforestry comprising oak (<i>Quercus robur</i>) and poplar (<i>Populus</i> spp.) with arable crops for food and feed
Domin Farm, Peickwitz, Germany	Mixed farming with cereals, cattle, poultry and pigs	A range of agroforestry systems to produce woodchips, poles, and timber
Tussen de Hagen, Stoutenburg, The Netherlands	Organic dairy farm, with cattle, poultry and pigs	Fodder hedge and nut and orchard alley cropping system
Kilpiän Tila, Uusimaa in southern Finland	Arable crops on an organic farm	Windbreak, riparian buffer strip, and orchard
Farm of Karel Ježek, Nová Říše, Czechia	Livestock farm with beef cattle	Silvopastoral agroforestry introducing Česká červinka cattle breed
Hope Farm, Knapwell, Cambridgeshire, United Kingdom	Conventional arable rotation	Silvoarable agroforestry in alley cropping system comprising apple, hazel and native broadleaved trees

2.4 Collection of biophysical and financial data on the agroforestry innovations

Biophysical and financial data on the agroforestry innovations were collected from the six Living Lab sites between October and December 2023 using a series of data collection templates. In order to support the data collection, one-to-one interviews were conducted with the farmers responsible for the specific sites. The results section of this report describes the agroforestry interventions and the input data for each of the sites.

3 Results

This section provides a brief summary of the agroforestry interventions being implemented/examined at each of the study sites, followed by an initial presentation of main financial benefits and costs. This section could be read along Milestone 8 to complement the baseline agricultural practices of the systems.

3.1 Italy

3.1.1 Case study farm

The Enrico Avanzi Research Centre is located within the "Migliarino - San Rossore - Massaciuccoli" Natural Park and the "Selve Costiere di Toscana" biosphere reserve in Tuscany in Italy (University of Pisa 2023). The research centre covers an area of 1400 hectares, extending from the town of San Piero a Grado to the sea. Since 1963, the centre has been managed by the University of Pisa to develop research and education in the fields of agricultural and veterinary sciences. The land quality is rated as 3 on a scale where 1 is low and 5 is high. The availability of water is rated as 2 on a scale where 1 in low and 5 is high.

3.1.2 Agroforestry innovation

The combination of perennial woody crops with herbaceous annual or perennial crops is being investigated as a method to increase the environmental, economic, and social sustainability and resilience of crop production to ongoing climate change. To achieve this, a long-term field experiment, known as ARNINO LTE (Long-Term Experiment) is being used to compare the effect of agroforestry on a three-year arable and a seven-year mixed crop rotation (Figure 1). The agroforestry innovation in Italy is a silvoarable system, composed of oak (*Quercus robur*) and poplar (*Populus spp.*) in combination with arable crops for the production food and feed.

Figure 2. Map of the agroforestry area of the ARNINO long-term experiment.

3.1.3 Financial data for agroforestry innovation

The main costs associated with the establishment of the poplar and oak silvoarable system in Italy are presented in Table 3. The costs of the trees was €2.50 each. In this initial analysis the establishment costs for poplar and oak were the same. At this stage, no costs of stump removal are available.

Table 3. Initial summary of costs for tree component of silvoarable system in Italy.

Cost category	Inputs	Units	Tree component	
			Poplar	Oak
Establishment	Tree planting density	(trees ha ⁻¹)	66	66
	Plant cost	(€ tree ⁻¹)	2.50	2.50
	Individual tree protection	(€ tree ⁻¹)	0	0
	Labour ground prep and weeding ^a	(€ tree ⁻¹)	1.33	1.33
	Labour for marking out	(hr ha ⁻¹)		
	Labour for planting trees ^a	(€ tree ⁻¹)	1.65	1.65
	Labour for tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	0	0
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)		
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	361.68	361.68
Irrigation	Cost of labour	(€ tree ⁻¹)	1.20	1.20
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	79.20	79.20
Weeding (annual)	Annual cost of weeding ^b	(€ tree ⁻¹)	0.69	0.69
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	45.54	45.54
Removing epicormics	Cost of labour	(€ tree ⁻¹)	1.10	1.10
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	72.60	72.60
Pruning	Height at first prune	(m)	1.50	1.50
	Height at last prune	(m)	5.00	5.00
	Cost of labour	(€ tree ⁻¹)	1.10	1.10
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	72.60	72.60
Stump removal costs	Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)	na	na
	Removal of tree stumps	(min tree ⁻¹)	na	na
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	-	-

^a: Includes excavation with auger for digging hole for planting seedlings. For poplar this includes a hole of 30 cm diameter and 1 m depth

^b: by localized manual mowing of weed plants

na: not available

The value of the main revenue sources of the silvoarable system in Italy are shown in Table 4. The table includes estimated rotation length and firewood value for poplar and oak. The felling value of the timber at harvest is still to be determined. This particular system received no planting grant. During future stages of the project, the plan is to use the results from Table 3 and Table 4 to determine the costs and benefits of agroforestry for the Italian case study.

Table 4. Initial summary of revenue for the tree component of the silvoarable system in Italy.

Input category	Inputs	Units	Tree component	
			Poplar	Oak
Prices (tree component)	Firewood value	(€ m ⁻³)	30 ^a	32.57 ^b
	Rotation	(y)	12	45
	Felling size	(m ⁻³)	na	na
	Felling value	(€ m ⁻³)	na	na
	Water content of wood	(%)	60	50
Planting payment	Year of planting grant	(year)	2018	2018
	Value of planting grant	(€ ha ⁻¹)	0	0

^a: http://www.al.camcom.gov.it/PriceLists/Pub/Item?id_level_2=8

^b: <https://legnonordovest.eu/report.html#prezzi-di-vendita-2022>

3.2.3 Financial data from agroforestry intervention

The main costs associated with the establishment and weeding of the short rotation coppice system in Germany are presented in Table 5. The cost of each plant varied between €0.20-€0.40. A detailed breakdown of the costs of trees is presented in the Appendix (Table 25).

The value of the main revenue sources of the silvoarable system in Germany are shown in Table 6. The table includes a woodchip value for poplar and Robinia extracted from a German database. The rotation varies between 4-5 years to 7-8 years depending on the plot. Poplar yields varied between plots, ranging from 26.84 to 109.01 t per ha. A detailed account of yields per plot and tree densities is included in the Appendix (

Table 26 and Table 27). The German SRC system received a planting grant only for poplar. At the time of data gathering no data was available for the orchard/fruit systems.

Table 5. Initial summary of costs for German short rotation coppice system.

	Units	Tree component			Mean
		Poplar 2015 ^a	Poplar Hybrid 275	Robinia ^b	
Number of trees per ha	(ha ⁻¹)	4176		4407	
Establishment costs					
Cost of plant	(€ tree ⁻¹)	0.24	0.20	0.41	
Cost of individual tree protection	(€ tree ⁻¹)	0		0	
Labour ground prep. and weeding ^d	(hr ha ⁻¹)				
Labour for marking out	(hr ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	
Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	0.26	0.26	0.38	
Labour tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	0	0	0	
Labour localised weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)				
Cost of labour ^e	(€ h ⁻¹)	80	80	80	
Sub-total					2948.00
Weed costs					
Year of first weeding	(year)	2015	2015	2015	
Year of last weeding	(year)	2016	2016	2016	
Annual labour for weeding	(h ha ⁻¹)	4.5	4.5	4.5	
Annual cost of weeding	(€ tree ⁻¹)				
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	135.00	135.00	135.00	135.00

^a: 20 cm length

^b: 1 year old rods

^c: tree density for alder = 2,756 trees ha⁻¹; willow = 2,314 trees ha⁻¹

^d: no prep PPM, b/c prices so expensive, prefer one more mechanical weeding, a lot of hand work

^e: with tractor and machine per hour incl. driver

Table 6. Initial estimates of revenue for the German short rotation coppice system.

		Poplar ^a	Robinia ^b	Hardwood mix	Alder ^b	Willow
Planting year	(y)	2015	2015	2020		
Rotation	(y)	4-8	4-8			
Yield	(t FM ha ⁻¹)	26.84- 109.01	49.38			
Timber value ^(c)	(€ DM m ⁻³)	23.50	23.50 9.00 ^(e)	^(d)		
Water content of wood chips	(%)	55 ^(f)	55 ^(f)			
Grants						
Planting grant ^(g)	(€ ha ⁻¹)	1,500	0	0		
2 nd planting grant ^(h)	(€ ha ⁻¹)	173	173	173	173	173
Maintenance grant ⁽ⁱ⁾	(€ ha ⁻¹)					

^a: Riparian buffer strip, fast growing on grassland

^b: Silvopastoral chicken run; from 2023, farmers are not allowed to plant Robinia anymore as it is on the list of banned tree species

^c: Prices for fresh weight would be €70 t⁻¹, this would be €220-230 t⁻¹ on a dry weight basis according to price database by CARMEN (2023).

^d: Value of timber in 40 years

^e: Value of timber for poles, etc.

^f: Value of fresh cut wood chips

^g: From 2024 onwards there will be a planting grant of species in short rotation systems of about 1,566 € per hectare (one-time payment). There was no planting grant available for planting hardwood mixtures in 2015; from 2024 onwards there will be a planting grant of species in short rotation systems of about 5.271 € (one-time payment)

^h: First Pillar payment (basic payment) for arable land is granted for the wooded area, this should be the same as in the arable crop database = currently €150 ha⁻¹

ⁱ: From 2023 on there is a maintenance payment EcoScheme #3 Agroforestry of 60€ per ha woody land, from 2024 this will be increased to 200 €/ha. However, the farmer will not receive it because the woody strips do not fully comply to the rules, but in theory he would get it. Robinia is excluded from the eco-scheme payment.

Taking the results from Table 5 and Table 6 it is possible to present a brief summary of the main costs per ha for the German SRC study case (Table 7). More detailed costs will be derived during the rest of the project.

Table 7. Summary table of financial benefits and costs of German short rotation coppice (SRC) system.

		Poplar SRC	Robinia SRC
Revenue	Woodchip yield ^a (t FM ha ⁻¹)	26 to 109	49
	Woodchip value (€ m ⁻³)	24	24
	Subsidies (€ ha ⁻¹)	1,673	173
Costs	Establishment (€ ha ⁻¹)	2,948	2,948
	Weeding (€ ha ⁻¹)	135	135

^a: Assumed yields on a four to eight year rotation

3.3 The Netherlands

3.3.1 Case study farm

The Dutch Farm is called “Tussen de Hagen” and is located in Stoutenburg, in the province of Utrecht. It is an organic dairy farm including 60 hectares of grassland and 12 hectares of crops. It encompasses a range of agroforestry systems including hedgerows, fodder trees and orchards.

3.3.2 Agroforestry innovation

The two agroforestry innovations on the Dutch farm are 3 hectares of nut trees, a small orchard (0.3 ha), and the inclusion of fodder trees. The 3 ha nut tree system includes hazelnut, chestnut, and walnut trees planted in rows with an alley spacing of 19 m (Figure 4). The orchard system includes fruit trees and hazelnut trees planted with an alley spacing of 20 m (Figure 5).

Figure 4. Nut field of Dutch agroforestry system.

Figure 5. Fruit field of Dutch agroforestry system.

3.3.3 Financial data for agroforestry innovation

The main costs associated with the establishment of the fodder hedge system in the Netherlands are presented in Table 8. A major cost was the purchase of a mechanical cutter for pruning (€5500).

Table 8. Initial summary of costs for the fodder hedge system in the Netherlands.

Costs	Units*	Fodder hedge	
Number of trees	(n)		2400
Length of hedge	(m)		600
Establishment			
Plant	(€ tree ⁻¹)		1.20
Individual tree protection	(€ m ⁻¹)	includes stakes, electric wire, insulators	0.20
Labour for ground preparation and weeding	(€ m ⁻¹)	Contract work: digging with crane 3 hours x €80/hour = €240 in total OR : 0.005 h m ⁻¹	0.40
Labour for marking out	(h m ⁻¹)	brainwork and actual marking = 5 hours in total	0.01
Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	Contract work (€75 hr ⁻¹): 10m ² h ⁻¹ = 40 trees h ⁻¹ = 1.5 min tree ⁻¹	1.51
Labour for tree protection	(min m ⁻¹)	OR = €1.875 tree ⁻¹ Protection per hedge, not per tree 4 hours per 600 m = 0.4 min m ⁻¹ OR 0.1 min tree ⁻¹	0.40
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)		30.00
Weeding			
Year of first weeding	(year)	Chickens have done the weeding: 2x in 2019, 1x in 2020	0.00
Sub-total	(€ m ⁻¹)		0.00
Pruning			
Pruning investment ^a	(€)	Mechanical cutter	5,500.00
Height at first prune	(m)	Hedge pruned annually at 3 meters height	3.00
Minutes per tree at first prune	(€ m ⁻¹)	Annual contract work with cyclo mower: 3 * €85 hr ⁻¹ 600 m ⁻¹ = €0.425 m ⁻¹	0.43
Minutes per tree at last prune	(€ m ⁻¹)	From 2024 onwards Estimation of labour costs (€30 hr ⁻¹): 10 hr 600 m ⁻¹ = 1 min m ⁻¹ = €0.50 m ⁻¹ excl. fuel & machinery costs	0.50
Administration			
Administrative cost of forestry	(€)	Admin in CAP (ANLb) costs 2 hours * €30 h ⁻¹ = €60 in total	60
Sub-total	(€ m ⁻¹)		0.10
Clear felling			
Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)	Estimation of labour costs for resetting the hedge	4
Removal of tree	(min tree ⁻¹)	excl. fuel and machinery	8
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)		30
Fuel costs	(€ m ⁻¹)	Fuel costs: 5 l h ⁻¹ * €4 l ⁻¹ * 40 h = €800 in total = €1.333 m ⁻¹	1.33
Management			
Labour	(min m ⁻¹)	Repairing tree protection: 4 hr y ⁻¹ = 0.4 min m ⁻¹	0.4
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)		30
Sub-total	(€ m ⁻¹)		0.20

* Units for the hedge system are given in terms of m per linear metre of hedge.

^a: The cost of investment or depreciation and fuel costs of machinery is not included

The value of the main revenue sources of the fodder system in the Netherlands are shown in Table 9. The land quality and water availability at the site was both rated as 5 on a five point scale where 1 is low and 5 is high. The table includes a firewood value for the fodder trees (willow, alder, hazel) and

estimated rotation length. The felling value of the timber at harvest has been estimated at €150 per cubic metre. The fodder system received a planting grant of €4.84 per linear metre.

Table 9. Initial summary of revenue sources for the fodder hedge system in the Netherlands^a. The fodder hedge is 600 m long, 1 m wide and 3 m tall.

Input category	Inputs	Units	Fodder hedge	
Calculation period		(y)		4 years old (start 2019)
Number of trees		(n)		2400
Length of hedge		(m)		600
Prices (tree component)	Firewood value	(€ m ⁻³)	Unknown, estimated value of light wood in 2040	150
	Rotation	(y)	21 years	21
	Felling size	(m ⁻³ tree ⁻¹)	Estimation: $\pi * 0.2^2 * 3 = 0.377 \text{ m}^3$ Other approach: hedge accumulates $\approx 400 \text{ kg DM y}^{-1} \rightarrow$ this hedge can produce accumulative yield of $\approx 40 \text{ t DW}$	0.38
	Felling value	(€ m ⁻³)	See above. Unknown, value of light wood in 2040. Estimation: €150	150
	Trees fell	(n m ⁻²)	4 per m ² , 2400 total	4
Planting grant	Year	(year)		2019
	Value	(€ m ⁻¹)	€4.84 per running meter	4.84
Maintenance payments	Initial year	(year)		2019
	Final year of receipt	(year)	Assuming extension of CAP	2040
	Amount	(€ m ⁻¹)	Per running meter, at least until 2028	2.80

^a: There are hidden gains in health livestock that have not been substantiated

Within the Dutch orchard system, the costs of each tree were high varying from €22.50 for hazel to €90.00 for walnut (Table 10).

Table 10. Input table of costs for tree component of agroforestry system (fruit species).

Cost	Inputs	Units	Apple/pear	Sweet chestnut	Walnut	Hazelnut	Average
	Establishment year	(y)	2020	2020	2020	2022	
	Number of trees	(n)	17	25	72	32	
	Tree density	(tree ha ⁻¹)	57	10	29	11.4	
Establishment	Cost of plant	(€ tree ⁻¹)	22.83	37.00	90.00	22.50	
	Description		Standard 2 y old (organic)	Seedling 3 y old 27.50 [2021] Grafted 1 y old	Grafted 2 y old 32.00 [2021] Grafted 1 y old	Grafted (organic)	
	Individual tree protection 2020 ^(a)	(€ tree ⁻¹)	6.37	6.37	6.37		
	Individual tree protection 2021 ^(b)	(€ tree ⁻¹)		3.52	3.52	3.52	
	Labour ground prep and weeding ^(c)	(hr ha ⁻¹)	1.1	1.1	1.1	1.1	
	Labour for marking out ^(d)	(hr ha ⁻¹)	5	5	5	5	
	Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	15	15	15	15	
	Labour for tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.5	
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	2,460.15	724.20	3,289.48	562.05	1758.97
Weeding costs	Year of first weeding	(year)	2019	2020	2020	2022	
	Annual labour for weeding ^(e)	(min tree ⁻¹)	Not needed	27	27	27	
	Annual cost of weeding ^(f)	(€ tree ⁻¹)		2.16	2.16	2.16	
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	0	21.60	62.64	24.62	36.29
Sward costs	Establishment of grass sward	(year)	1997				
Removal of epicormics	Year of first removal of epicormics	(year)	2019	2020	2020	2022	
	Labour for removal of epicormics ^(g)	(min tree ⁻¹)	0.5	0.5	0.5	0.5	
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	14.25	2.50	7.25	2.85	6.71
Pruning	Year of first prune	(year)	2022	2022	2022	2022	
	Minutes per tree at 1 st prune ^(h)	(min tree ⁻¹)	15	15	15	15	
	Minutes per tree at last prune ^(g)	(min tree ⁻¹)	45	45	45	45	
	Removal of prunings ⁽ⁱ⁾	(min tree ⁻¹)	0	0	0	0	
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	1,710.00	300.00	870.00	342.00	805.50

Table 10 (continued). Input table of costs for tree component of agroforestry system (fruit species).

Cost	Inputs	Units	Apple/pear	Sweet chestnut	Walnut	Hazelnut	Average
Harvesting	Year of first harvest ^(j)	(year)	-	-	-	-	-
	Labour for first harvest ^(g)	(h tree ⁻¹ y ⁻¹)	0.5	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
	Year of final harvest ^(k)	(year)	-	-	-	-	-
	Labour for final harvest	(h tree ⁻¹ y ⁻¹)	1	1	1	1	1
	Cost of labour	(€ hr ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	30
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	855.00	60.00	174.00	68.40	289.35
Sales	Other sale costs ^(k)	(€ yr ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Irrigation	Irrigation investment ^(l)	(€ ha ⁻¹)	442.86	442.86	442.86	442.86	442.86
	Irrigation costs ^(m)	(€ yr ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
	Labour for irrigation	(h ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	442.86	442.86	442.86	442.86	442.86
Clearing	Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)	60	60	60	60	60
	Removal of tree	(min tree ⁻¹)	120	120	120	120	120
	Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	30
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	205,200.00	36,000.00	104,400.00	41,040.00	96,660.00
Management	Labour ⁽ⁿ⁾	(h ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
	Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Comments	We miss cells for investment costs and depreciation costs						

^(a) 49x tree pole (3.90), tree strap (0.40), mesh (0.74) = 5.04 [2020]; stakes + electric wire + insulators = €0.195 per running meter * 75 m row, 1 * 10 rows / 110 trees = 1.33

^(b) 73x bamboo (1.34), elastic tie (0.85) = 2.19 [2021/22]; stakes + electric wire + insulators = €0.195 per running meter * 75 m row, 1 * 10 rows / 110 trees = 1.33

^(c) 3 h for 2.8 ha

^(d) 14 h for 2.8 ha

^(e) Brush cutter, about 50 ha per year

^(f) Fuel = 1.2 l h⁻¹ * €4 l⁻¹ * (27/60) = €2.16 tree⁻¹

^(g) Estimate

^(h) About 30 h y⁻¹

⁽ⁱ⁾ Prunings will stay on field

^(j) Harvest is not yet significant, estimated 2025

^(k) Unknown

^(l) €1150 for 750m drip irrigation system incl. connections + 3 hours * €30 hr⁻¹ = €1240

^(m) Unknown; consists of water use and electricity or fuel for pump

⁽ⁿ⁾ See Excel with pasture management costs we filled in earlier; grazing pastures keeps same; mowing pastures costs 10% more labour and fuel

At the time of writing the value of the fruit anticipated within the Dutch orchard system is uncertain (Table 11). The anticipated firewood value from the apple trees is estimated to be 200 € m⁻³ at felling after about 50 years. The CAP (ANLb) funded 50% of the cost of nut trees on the first year of planting (2020) and the second planting year (2021) 100% of the tree costs were covered by the local Environmental federation (NMU).

Table 11. Initial summary of revenue sources for Dutch orchard system (2.8 ha; 146 trees).

		Unit	Value	Comment
Revenue	Firewood	(m ³ tree ⁻¹)	1	Estimation after 50 years
		(€ m ⁻³)	200	Estimate
	Fruit quantity	(kg tree ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)		Unknown
	Fruit value (Apples 1)	(€ kg ⁻¹)		Unknown
	Fruit value (Apples 2)	(€ kg ⁻¹)		Expected quality 2 fruit for juice
	Nut value	(€ kg ⁻¹)		Nut quality will determine values
Grants	Year of planting grant	(year)		No grant for fruit trees (2019) 1 st year (2020) 50% of tree costs covered by CAP (ANLb). 2 nd year (2021) 100% tree costs covered by local Environmental federation (NMU)

Taking the results from Table 8, Table 9, Table 10 and Table 11 it is possible to present a brief summary of the main costs per ha for the Dutch study case (Table 12). It is noted that the clearing costs for the trees are high and the appropriateness of this value will be reviewed in the Roadmap 2.0 report.

Table 12. Summary of benefits and costs of agroforestry innovation in the Netherlands

	Fodder system		Fruit & nut system	
Characteristics	Number of trees	2,400	Number of trees	146
	Length of hedge	600		
Subsidies	Grant (€ m ⁻¹)	7.6	Grant nut trees 2020 (€ ha ⁻¹)	2,288
			Grant nut trees 2021 (€ ha ⁻¹)	4,576
Prices*	Firewood (€ m ⁻³)	150		200
	Timber (€ m ⁻³)	150		-
Costs	Establishment (€ m ⁻¹)	51.1	Establishment (€ ha ⁻¹)	1,759
	Weeding (€ m ⁻¹)	0.00	Weeding (€ ha ⁻¹)	36
			Sward (€ ha ⁻¹)	-
			Epicormic (€ ha ⁻¹)	7
	Pruning (€ m ⁻¹)	10.1	Pruning (€ ha ⁻¹)	806
			Harvesting (€ ha ⁻¹)	289
			Sale (€ ha ⁻¹)	-
	Admin (€ m ⁻¹)	0.1	Maintenance (€ ha ⁻¹)	443
	Clear-felling (€ m ⁻¹)	25.3	Clearing (€ ha ⁻¹)	96,660
	Management (€ m ⁻¹)	0.2	Management (€ ha ⁻¹)	-

3.4 Finland

3.4.1 Case study farm

The selected farm in Finland is Kilpiän Tila, which is a 75 ha arable organic farm focused on cereal production in the region of Uusimaa in southern Finland. The land quality and availability of water were both rated as 4 on a five point scale ranging from 1 is low to 5 is high.

3.4.2 Agroforestry practices

The main motivation for introducing agroforestry was for reducing erosion and restoring soil health on the farm. The systems introduced are windbreaks and a fruit tree orchard (Figure 6). The motivation of the smaller windbreak in the south-east corner of the farm was for preventing the spread of herbicides (mainly glyphosate) from the neighbouring farm. The Living Lab farm is an organic farm, but when herbicides are spread on the neighbouring farm they could drift because of wind. In this case, wind break 3 has a function as a barrier.

Figure 6. Map showing a 25 ha section of the Finnish case study farm showing the areas of agroforestry.

Of the total farm area of 75 ha (not shown in the figure), about 25 ha are under agroforestry comprising 24 ha under cereal cultivation and a 1 ha fruit tree orchard.

Fruit tree orchard: one hectare orchard composed of apples (300 trees), pears (200 trees) walnut (50 trees) and hazelnut (30 trees), positioned along contour lines (to prevent erosion) (Figure 7). Winter rye and spring crops are sown under the trees in a four-year rotation. Year 1: rye, undersown with green manure mixture (nitrogen fixers and grasses); year 2 comprised green manure ley; year 3 was spring crop (spelt, oats or pea) late cultivation and sowing of winter rye, and in year 4 the rotation returns to year 1.

Windbreak 1: 2 m wide and 391 m long windbreak composed of willow (planting distance every 50 cm)(area 0.11 ha) and black alder *Alnus glutinosa* (planting distance every 5 m). Willow is for basket making and alder is for timber production for furniture making in the future. The field is sown with winter rye and spring oats in a 4- year rotation (rye, green manure ley, spring crop). In the centre part of the windbreak also some walnut and hazelnut seedlings are planted.

Windbreak 2a and 2b: Two windbreaks in V shape (length windbreak 2a: 238 m, length windbreak 2b: 348 m) planted with sea-buckthorn *Hippophae rhamnoides* (200 pcs.).

Windbreak 3: Sixty-meter-long windbreak in the south-east corner of the field planted with Siberian larch (30 pcs.), birch (30 pcs.) and hazel (30 pcs.).

Figure 7. Diagram of orchard agroforestry design in the Finnish case study.

3.4.3 Financial data from Agroforestry innovation

The main costs associated with the establishment of the windbreak system in Finland are presented in Table 13. The costs of trees varied between €0.50 and €1.50 per tree.

Table 13. Input table of costs for tree component of agroforestry system (windbreak species).

Costs	Units	Tree component				
		Willow	Alder	Birch	Larch	Mean
Establishment						
Cost of plant	(€ tree ⁻¹)	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.50	
Cost of mulching ^(a)	(€ tree ⁻¹)	0.30	0.30	0.30	0.30	
Labour ground prep and weeding	(hr ha ⁻¹)	1	1	1	1	
Labour for marking out	(hr ha ⁻¹)	1	1	1	1	
Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	2	2	2	2	
Labour for tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	1	1	2.6 ^(b)		
Labour for localised weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	0	0	0	0	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	78.63	68.96	61.80	61.40	67.70
Weeding						
Year of first weeding	(year)					
Year of last weeding	(year)	-				
Annual labour for weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	1	1	1	1	
Annual cost of weeding	(€ tree ⁻¹)					
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	4.05	1.60	0.25	0.25	1.54
Sward costs						
Establishment of grass sward	(year)	No sward	Naturally regenerated	Rye; no cost	Rye; no cost	
Labour for grass sward establishment	(hr ha ⁻¹ grass)	0	0	0	0	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	0	0	0	0	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	0	0	0	0	0
Epicormics removal						
First year of removal	(year)	-	2015	-	-	
Last year of removal	(year)		2022			
Labour for removal of epicormics	(min tree ⁻¹)		1			
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)		30			
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	-	1.60	-	-	1.60
Thinning						
Marking-up and labour	(min tree ⁻¹)		-	-	-	
Removal of tree	(min tree ⁻¹)		-	-	-	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)		30	30	30	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Coppicing[©]						
Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	50	50	50		
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Clear felling /removal						
Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)				-	-
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)				50	-
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Management^(d)						
Labour	(h ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)					

They haven't cut any trees and they are also not planning to cut trees in the near future

^(a) Total cost of mulching material was €100 for all trees: 100/(195+78+30+30)=0.30

^(b) 4h for 90 trees

^(c) Every 5 years

^(d) Considered insignificant compared to management of arable enterprise

The value of the main revenue sources of the windbreak system includes a firewood value for birch and a bioenergy value for willow (Table 14). Felling values of the timber at harvest are based on current prices per cubic metre (60-90 € m⁻³). No grants were available at the time of establishment of the windbreak system.

Table 14. Initial summary of potential revenue from windbreak in Finland (windbreak species*).

	Unit	Willow ^(a)	Alder ^(a)	Birch ^(b)	Siberian larch ^(b)
Tree density	(trees ha ⁻¹) (trees m ⁻¹)	8.10 ^(c)	3.20 ^(d)	0.50 ^(e)	0.50 ^(e)
Rotation	(y)	5	30-50	30-50	50
Firewood value	(€ m ⁻³)			100.00	
By-product value	(€ t ⁻¹)				
Felling size	(m ³ tree ⁻¹)		0.16	0.27	0.28
Dbh at felling	(cm)		15	20	19.5
Yield	(m ³ ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	12-18			
	(t DM ha ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	6.0-9.0			
Felling value	(€ m ⁻³)	7.44 ^(f)	90 ^(g)	60 ^(g)	70
Water content of wood	(%)	50	50	50	50
Year of planting	(year)	2013	2013	2023	2023
Planting grant	(€ ha ⁻¹)	0	0	0	0

Comments: The surface area of the willow windbreak is 0.11 ha; the productivity in 5 years is 3,300 – 4,950 kg DM (6000 – 9000 kg DM ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ x 0.11 ha x 5yrs). The price of willow depends on the use; bioenergy is €7.44 m⁻³; willow for basket making is €10 kg⁻¹

* there is hazelnut as well in the windbreak but only 60 trees divided between windbreak 1 and 3, therefore not considered relevant for this exercise

^(a) Part of windbreak 1 (green line in farm map, Figure 6)

^(b) Part of windbreak 3

^(c) 195 trees on 24 ha

^(d) 78 trees on 24 ha

^(e) 30 trees on a 60 m strip

^(f) price for bioenergy

^(g) only selling thinning timber from alder and birch

The main costs associated with the establishment of the orchard system in Finland are presented in Table 15. The costs of each tree varied between €3 for pear and €15 for hazel.

Table 15. Initial summary of costs for the orchard system in Finland

Cost	Units	Apple	Pear	Buckthorn (a)	Hazel	Walnut ^(b) / blackcurrant
Tree density	(trees ha ⁻¹) (trees m ⁻¹)	300	200	0.34 ^(c)	30	50
Establishment						
Cost of plant	(€ tree ⁻¹)	10	3	10	15	5
Cost of individual tree protection	(€ tree ⁻¹)	2	2	1	0	0
Labour ground prep and weeding	(hr ha ⁻¹)	10	10	2	0	0
Labour for marking out	(hr ha ⁻¹)	2	2	2	0	0
Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	5	5
Labour for tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	0	0
Labour for localised weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	1	1	1	1	1
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	30
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	5610.00	2460.00	125.63	540.00	400.00
Weeding						
Year of first weeding	(year)	2014	2020	2020	2020	2020
Year of last weeding	(year)	2023	2023	2023	2023	2023
Annual labour for weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8	1.8
Annual cost of weeding	(€ tree ⁻¹)	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	30
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	270.00	180.00	0.31	27.00	45.00
Sward costs						
Establishment of grass sward	(year)	2013	2019	2019	2019	Na
Labour for sward establishment ^(d)	(hr ha ⁻¹ grass)	0.5 ^(e)	0.2 ^(f)	0.09 ^(g)	0.08 ^(h)	0
Materials for sward establishment	(€ ha ⁻¹ grass)	30	30	20	0	0
Final year of sward	(year)					
Labour for sward maintenance	(hr ha ⁻¹ grass)	3	3	-	3	3
Materials for sward maintenance	(€ ha ⁻¹ grass)	30	30	-	30	30
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30	30	30	30
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	165.00	156.00	4.98	122.50	120.00
Epicormic removal						
Year of first removal	(year)	-	-	-	-	-
Year of last removal	(year)	-	-	-	-	-
Labour for removal	(min tree ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Pruning costs						
Height at first prune	(m)	1,5	1			
Minutes per tree at first prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	2	1			
Height at last prune	(m)	2	1.5			
Minutes per tree at last prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	5.5	1			
Removal of prunings	(min tree ⁻¹)	0-1	0			
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	30	30			
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	300	100	-	-	-
Stump removal						
Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Removal of tree stumps	(min tree ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	50 ⁽ⁱ⁾	50	50	50	50
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)					
Management						
Labour	(h ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	-
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)					

na: not applicable

(a) Part of windbreak 2; (b) Part of windbreak 1 (purple line in farm map, Figure 6); (c) 200 trees in 238 m plus 348 m, 3 m wide; (d) 30 min ha; (e) spread by tractor mounted machine; (f) 0.4 ha, spread using hand equipment; (g) 0.18 ha; (h) 5 min; (i) done by contractor

The value of the main revenue sources of the orchard system in Finland are shown in Table 16. Due to the recent establishment of the system, no fruit has been sold as of yet; indicated fruit prices have been estimated based on half the retail price. No grant was available for this particular system at the time of establishment.

Table 16. Initial summary of the anticipated revenue from the orchard system in Finland.

	Unit	Apple (a)	Pear (a)	Sea buckthorn (b)	Hazel	Walnut
Fruit yield (e)	(kg ha ⁻¹)	4,122 (f)		4,750 (g)		
	(kg tree ⁻¹)		67.5 (h)		4 (i)	6 (i)
Fruit value (c)	(€ t ⁻¹)	1,590	1,250	9,000	7,000	8,000
Fruit value (juice and jam) (d)	(€ t ⁻¹)					
Fruit value	(€ kg ⁻¹)	Pick yourself	Pick yourself	Pick yourself	Pick yourself	Pick yourself
Planting year	(year)	2013	2019	2019	2020-23	2020-23
Value of grant	(€ ha ⁻³)	0	0	0	0	0

* Orchard distributed in an area of 1 ha

(a) Farmer planning to sell scion wood in the future

(b) Farmer planning to sell tea and jam in the future

(c) Current fruit production is for self-consumption, price indicated is half of retail price; selling next year onwards

(d) Planning direct sell to consumer once it is in production

(e) Estimates

(f) Source: Omenan viljelyn kannattavuus, presentation ProAgria. Yield is from Uusimaa region

(g) Yield is from Tyrni viljely, 2015 available online at:

https://jukuri.luke.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/518880/luke-luobio_45_2015.pdf?sequence=4&isAllowed=y

(h) From: <https://wikifarmer.com/pear-tree-harvest-and-yield/> however, this is highly variable

(i) In Serbia, 3-5 kg per tree from year 7-15, and 5-10 kg/tree from year 15-25. For Finland no data available but probably lower yield: <https://www.hazelnut.co.rs/en/production>

(j) 7-10 kg/tree in year 5-7. 30-160 kg during the peak production around year 30. In Finland no data on yield available. However, probably much lower yields can be expected <https://wikifarmer.com/walnut-tree-harvest-yields/>

Taking the results from Table 13, Table 14, Table 15, and Table 16 it is possible to present a brief summary of the main costs per ha for the Finnish study case (Table 17).

Table 17. Summary table of financial benefits and costs of the Finnish case study.

Agroforestry system	Windbreak		Fruit	
Subsidies (€ ha ⁻¹)		0		0
Yields / potential yields*	Firewood (€ m ⁻³)	0	Fruit yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
	Willow biomass (€ m ⁻³)	7	Stone fruit value (€ ha ⁻¹)	1,420
	Alder and birch thinnings (€ m ⁻³)	75	Sea blackthorn value (€ ha ⁻¹)	9,000
	Siberian larch timber (€ m ⁻³)	70	Nut value (€ ha ⁻¹)	7,500
Costs	Establishment (€ ha ⁻¹)	68	Establishment stone fruit (€ ha ⁻¹)	4,035
			Establishment sea buckthorn (€ ha ⁻¹)	3,420
	Weeding (€ ha ⁻¹)	2	Establishment nuts (€ ha ⁻¹)	470
			Weeding stone fruit (€ ha ⁻¹)	225
	Sward (€ ha ⁻¹)	0	Weeding sea buckthorn (€ ha ⁻¹)	180
			Weeding nuts (€ ha ⁻¹)	36
	Epicormic (€ ha ⁻¹) ^(a)	2	Sward stone fruit (€ ha ⁻¹)	161
			Sward sea buckthorn (€ ha ⁻¹)	5
	Thinning (€ ha ⁻¹)	-	Sward nuts (€ ha ⁻¹)	121
	Coppicing (€ ha ⁻¹)	-	Epicormic (€ ha ⁻¹)	-
	Clear-felling and removal (€ ha ⁻¹)	-	Pruning stone fruit (€ ha ⁻¹)	200
			Stump-removal (€ ha ⁻¹)	-
	Land management (€ ha ⁻¹)	-	Land management (€ ha ⁻¹)	-

*in cases when system was too young at the time of data gathering

(a) Only applicable to alder

3.5 Czechia

3.5.1 Case study farm

The farm of Karel Ježek is located near the town of Nová Říše in the Bohemian-Moravian Highlands of Czechia. The farm is certified for organic farming. The land quality rating was 2 on a five point scale from 1 is low to 5 is high. The water availability was rated as 3 on a five point scale from 1 is low to 5 is high.

3.5.2 Agroforestry innovation

By establishing an agroforestry system (ALS) on permanent grasslands (the so-called silvopastoral agroforestry system) on the farm, the farmer aimed to strengthen the diversification of agricultural production by planting forest and fruit trees on permanent grasslands. The goal is the production of wood and timber in the long term and quality fruit production in the short term with the simultaneous production of quality hay and hay on the given plots. Thanks to this measure, they expect an increase in biodiversity on the planted plots. The site will become home to many species of insects, birds and mammals. For the farmer, it was also important the aesthetic character of the landscape granted with the planting of trees and the improvement of the adaptability of land and landscape to ongoing climate changes (water retention, cooling of the landscape). In this instance, the farmer wishes to change the cattle breed to Česká červinka in order to preserve this rare Czech breed and to benefit from local subsidies.

A silvopastoral system covering 9.6 ha combining cattle, timber and fruit trees was established in 2023 in three stages on three blocks of meadow (3.2 ha, 2.3 ha, 4.2 ha). The trees will be planted following a north-south orientation in alleys of 18-20 m lines and an intra-tree row distance of 3-6 m, to create a density of 100 trees per hectare (Figure 8 a), b), c)). Tree lines are 18-20m away from field boundaries. The tree species selected comprise a mix of high-value timber trees, such as 300 pedunculate oak (*Quercus robur*), 300 sycamore (*Acer pseudoplatanus*), and 50 alder (*Alnus glutinosa*); and fruit trees such as 185 plum (*Prunus domestica*), 80 apple (*Malus domestica*), 30 pear (*Pyrus communis*), and 20 sour cherry (*Prunus cerasus*). In total, when the implementation is completed, the design will consist of almost 1000 trees. Trees (of at least 120 cm) were obtained from local tree nurseries (Lesoškolky s.r.o., Řečany nad Labem, Šťastný, Hněvkovice). Grass will be cut around the planted trees.

The design of the agroforestry innovation in the Czech case study farm is illustrated in Figure 8 for the three stages.

a) Design of stage 1, from left to right, the lines of trees contain:

- oak, maple, alder, sour cherry, apple, pear
- oak, maple, alder, apple, and plum

b) Design of stage 2, from left to right, the lines of trees contain:

- oak, maple, alder, sour cherry, apple
- oak, maple, alder, pear, apple
- oak, maple, alder, apple, plum

c) Design of stage 2, from left to right, the lines of trees contain:

- oak, maple, sour cherry, apple
- oak, maple, pear, apple
- oak, maple, apple
- oak, maple, apple
- oak, maple, alder, apple, plum
- oak, maple, alder, apple, plum

Figure 8. Design of the agroforestry innovation followed in Czechia; a) first stage on field of 3.2 ha; b) second stage on field of 2.3 ha; c) third stage on field of 4.2 ha.

3.5.3 Financial data from agroforestry innovation

The main costs associated with the establishment of the silvopastoral system in Czechia are presented in Table 19. The costs of trees varied between €3.9 and €4.9 per tree.

The value of the main revenue sources of the silvopastoral system are shown in Table 18. The table includes estimated rotation length and a firewood value of €120 per cubic metre for all species. Felling values of the timber at harvest are based on current prices per cubic metre (€2,000-€4,000). The silvoarable system received a grant of €754 per ha.

Table 18. Initial summary of the revenue from the tree component of the Czech silvopastoral system. The area is 3.2 ha and the tree density is 100 trees per hectare.

Input category	Inputs	Units	Tree component		
			Oak (280)	Maple (280)	Alder (50)
Species (number of trees)					
Prices (tree component)	Rotation	(y)	80	60	40
	Firewood value	(m ⁻³ tree)	1.5	1.5	1.5
	Firewood value	(€ m ⁻³)	120	120	120
	Felling size	(m ⁻³)	1	1	1
	Felling value	(€ m ⁻³)	4,000	4,000	2,000
Planting payment	Year of planting grant	(year)	2023	2023	2023
	Value of planting grant	(€ ha ⁻¹)	4,353	4,353	4,353
Maintenance payments	Initial year of receipt	(year)	2024	2024	2024
	Final year of receipt	(year)	2028	2028	2028
	Amount	(€ ha ⁻¹)	754	754	754

Table 19. Input table of costs for tree component of the Czech silvopastoral system.

Inputs	Units	Tree component			
		Oak (280)	Maple (280)	Alder (50)	average
Establishment ^(a)					
Cost of plant	(€ tree ⁻¹)	4.84	4.62	3.85	
Cost of individual tree protection	(€ tree ⁻¹)	2.5	2.5	2.5	
Labour for marking out	(hr ha ⁻¹)	3	3	3	
Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	22	22	22	
Labour for tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	11	11	11	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	13	13	13	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	1459	1,437	1,360	1,419
Weeding					
Year of first weeding	(year)	2024	2024	2024	
Year of last weeding	(year)	-	-	-	
Annual labour for weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	20	20	20	
Annual cost of weeding	(€ tree ⁻¹)	4	4	4	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	13	13	13	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	417	417	417	417
Epicormic removal					
Year of first removal	(year)	2024	2024	2024	
Labour for removal	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	13	13	13	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	104	104	104	104
Pruning					
Minutes per tree at first prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	
Height at first prune	(m)	2	2	2	
Height at last prune	(m)	5	5	5	
Minutes per tree at last prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	10	10	10	
Removal of prunings	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	13	13	13	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	417	417	417	417
Irrigation ^(b)					
Labour for irrigation	(h ha ⁻¹)	20	20	20	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	20	20	20	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	400	400	400	400
Clear felling ^(c)					
Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)	20	20	20	
Removal of tree	(min tree ⁻¹)	10	10	10	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	20	20	20	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000
Stump removal					
Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)	20	20	20	
Removal of tree stumps	(min tree ⁻¹)	10	10	10	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	20	20	20	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	1,000	1,000	1,000	1,000

^(a): Added 10% to costs of tree establishment due to cost associated with replacing failed trees.

^(b): For the first three years following establishment; estimated values.

^(c): Felling after 60 years

The main costs associated with the establishment of the Czech orchard system are presented in Table 20. The cost of all fruit trees was the same, €6.38 per tree.

Table 20. Input table of costs for tree component of orchard system in Czechia.

Inputs	Units	Tree component				average
		Plum	Apple	Pear	Sour cherry	
Tree density	(Trees ha ⁻¹)	200	100	30	20	
Establishment ^(a)						
Cost of plant	(€ tree ⁻¹)	6.38	6.38	6.38	6.38	
Cost of individual tree protection	(€ tree ⁻¹)	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	
Labour for marking out	(hr ha ⁻¹)	3	3	3	3	
Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	33	33	33	33	
Labour for tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	11	11	11	11	
Labour for localised weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	0	0	0	0	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	13	13	13	13	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	1,842	1,842	1,842	1,842	1,842
Weeding						
Year of first weeding	(year)	2024	2024	2024	2024	
Year of last weeding	(year)	-	-	-	-	
Annual labour for weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	20	20	20	20	
Annual cost of weeding	(€ tree ⁻¹)	4.2	4.2	4.2	4.2	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	13	13	13	13	
Sub-total		417	417	417	417	417
Epicormic removal						
Year of first removal	(year)	2024	2024	2024	2024	
Year of last removal	(year)					
Labour for removal	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	5	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	13	13	13	13	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	104	104	104	104	104
Pruning						
Height at first prune	(m)	-	-	-	-	
Minutes per tree at first prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	5	
Height at last prune	(m)	-	-	-	-	
Minutes per tree at last prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	20	20	20	20	
Removal of prunings	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	5	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	13	13	13	13	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	625	625	625	625	625
Irrigation ^(b)						
Labour for irrigation	(h ha ⁻¹)	20	20	20	20	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	20	20	20	20	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	400	400	400	400	400
Stump removal						
Labour	(min tree ⁻¹)	20	20	20	20	
Removal of tree stumps	(min tree ⁻¹)	10	10	10	10	-
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	20	20	20	20	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	1000	1000	1000	1000	1000
Management						
Labour	(h ha ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	-	-	-	-	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)					

^(a) Added 10% to costs of tree establishment due to cost associated with replacing failed trees.

^(b) For the first three years following establishment; estimated values.

The value of the main revenue sources of the orchard system in Czechia are shown in Table 21. Due to the recent establishment of the system, no fruit has been sold yet; indicated fruit prices have been estimated based on current retail price. The orchard system benefited from a planting grant of €4,353 and a maintenance grant of €754.

Table 21. Initial summary of revenue from tree component of Czech orchard system (100 trees ha⁻¹).

Tree component						
Tree species (number of trees)	Name (n)	Plum (200)	Apple (100)	Pear (30)	Sour cherry (20)	Mean
Fruit quantity per tree	(kg tree ⁻¹)	60	100	100	35	
Fruit quantity	(€ kg ⁻¹)	6	3.5	6	7.5	
Fruit value	(€ t ⁻¹)	6,000	3,500	6,000	7,500	5,750
Fruit yield	(t ha ⁻¹)	6	10	10	3.5	7.38
Yield value	(€ ha ⁻¹)	36,000	35,000	60,000	26,250	39,312
Year of planting grant	(year)	2023	2023	2023	2023	
Value of planting grant	(€ ha ⁻¹)	4,353	4,353	4,353	4,353	4353
Initial year of receipt	(year)	2024	2024	2024	2024	
Final year of receipt	(year)	2028	2028	2028	2028	
Amount	(€ ha ⁻¹)	754	754	754	754	754

Taking the results from Table 19, The value of the main revenue sources of the silvopastoral system are shown in Table 18. The table includes estimated rotation length and a firewood value of €120 per cubic metre for all species. Felling values of the timber at harvest are based on current prices per cubic metre (€2,000-€4,000). The silvoarable system received a grant of €754 per ha.

Table 18, Table 20, and Table 21 it is possible to present a brief summary of the main costs per ha for the Czech study case (Table 22).

Table 22. Summary table of financial benefits and costs of the Czech case study.

Agroforestry system	Timber		Fruit	
Subsidies (€ ha ⁻¹)		5,107		5,107
Yields / potential yields*	Firewood (€ m ⁻³)	1.5	Fruit yield (t ha ⁻¹)	7.4
	By-product (€ m ⁻³)	120	Fruit value (€ ha ⁻¹)	5,750
	Oak/sycamore timber (€ m ⁻³)	4,000		
	Alder timber (€ m ⁻³)	2,000		
Costs	Establishment (€ ha ⁻¹)	1,419	Establishment (€ ha ⁻¹)	1,842
	Weeding (€ ha ⁻¹)	417	Weeding (€ ha ⁻¹)	417
	Epicormic (€ ha ⁻¹)	104	Epicormic (€ ha ⁻¹)	104
	Pruning (€ ha ⁻¹)	417	Pruning (€ ha ⁻¹)	625
	Irrigation (€ ha ⁻¹)	400	Irrigation (€ ha ⁻¹)	400
	Thinning (€ ha ⁻¹)	-	Stump-removal (€ ha ⁻¹)	1,000
	Clear-felling (€ ha ⁻¹)	1,000	Land management (€ ha ⁻¹)	-
	Stump-removal (€ ha ⁻¹)	1,000		
	Land management (€ ha ⁻¹)	-		

*in cases when system was too young at the time of data gathering.

3.6 United Kingdom

3.6.1 Case study farm

For the UK case study farm is Hope Farm located in Knapwell, Cambridgeshire in Eastern England. It is a 181 ha commercially managed arable farm owned by the Royal Society for the Protection of Birds (RSPB).

3.6.2 Agroforestry innovation

Within the 181 ha of the farm, one 11 ha field has been allocated to silvoarable agroforestry with the objective of increasing farm biodiversity and diversifying farm outputs (Figure 9). The silvoarable system, established by staff and volunteers, is an alley-cropping system using three types of trees (Figure 10), in total 1,000 trees:

- Apple trees of 13 varieties
- Cobnut trees of 3 varieties
- Broadleaf shelterbelt trees of six species to provide a wind break, consisting of field maple, small leaved lime, hornbeam, wild cherry, hawthorn, and common alder

Figure 9. Aerial view of farm boundary (red) and agroforestry field (yellow) at Hope Farm, Cambridgeshire, UK.

Figure 10. Diagram of agroforestry design in the British case study.

3.6.3 Financial data from Agroforestry innovation

The main costs associated with the establishment of the silvoarable system in the UK are presented in Table 24. The costs of trees varied between €1.15 for the native broadleaf species to €17.90 for each apple tree.

The value of the main revenue sources of the alley cropping system are shown in the brief summary table for the British case study (Table 23). Due to the recent establishment of the system (2021), the apple yield indicated is an estimation based on a nearby farm in the same region of England and the apple price has been obtained from a British database (2023 prices). No reliable source of data for hazelnuts was found at the time of data gathering. The silvoarable system received a grant of €66 per ha.

Table 23. Initial summary of the benefits and costs of the silvoarable system in the UK.

Agroforestry system	Silvoarable (fruit)	
Subsidies	(€ ha ⁻¹)	66
Potential apple yields	(t ha ⁻¹)	0.5 ^(a)
Apple price	(€ kg ⁻¹)	1.3 ^(b)
Costs	Establishment (€ ha ⁻¹)	3590
	Weeding (€ ha ⁻¹)	131
	Wild flower strips (€ ha ⁻¹)	384
	Pruning (€ ha ⁻¹)	369
	Maintenance (€ ha ⁻¹)	92

^(a) Based on yields obtained at Whitehall Farm (Cambridgeshire, UK)

^(b) Price extracted from <https://www.gov.uk/government/statistical-data-sets/wholesale-fruit-and-vegetable-prices-weekly-average> for gala apples (lowest price)

Table 24. Input table of costs for tree component of the British silvoarable system (field area: 11 ha; tree area = 1.63 ha; exchange rate: 1.15 €/£)

Inputs	Units	Tree component			
		Apple	Cobnut	Native broadleaves	Mean
Number of trees	(n)	200	600	200	
Tree density	(n ha ⁻¹)	90.91	90.91	90.91	
Establishment					
Cost of plant 1st year	(€ tree ⁻¹)	17.85	14.97	1.15	
Cost of plant 2nd year	(€ tree ⁻¹)	36.86			
Cost of plant replacement	(€ tree ⁻¹)		17.85		
Cost of individual tree protection	(€ tree ⁻¹)	7.10	5.76	2.97	
Labour for ground prep and weeding ^(a)	(hr ha ⁻¹)	1.6	1.6	0.8	
Labour for marking out ^(a)	(hr ha ⁻¹)	11.9	12.1	6	
Labour for planting trees	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	3	
Labour for tree protection	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	3	
Labour for localised weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	0	0	0	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	17.28	17.28	17.28	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	6,114	4,007	649	3,590
Weeding					
Year of first weeding	(year)	2022	2022	2022	
Year of last weeding	(year)	2023	2023	2023	
Annual labour for weeding	(min tree ⁻¹)	5	5	5	
Annual cost of weeding	(€ tree ⁻¹)	383.58	767.17	287.98	
Cost of labour	(€ h ⁻¹)	17.28	17.28	17.28	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	131	131	131	131
Wildflower strips ^(b)					
Establishment of wild flowers strips	(year)	2021	2021	2021	
Materials for wild flower establishment	(€ ha ⁻¹)	456.73	463.52	231.76	
Labour for wild flower maintenance	(h ha ⁻¹)	1.6	1.6	0.8	
Cost of labour ^(c)	(€ h ⁻¹)	0.00	0.00	0.00	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	456	463	232	384
Pruning					
Height at first prune ^(d)	(m)	2	-	-	
Minutes per tree at first prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	15	-	-	
Height at last prune ^(e)	(m)	-	-	-	
Minutes per tree at last prune	(min tree ⁻¹)	-	-	-	
Removal of prunings ^(f)	(min tree ⁻¹)	1.00	1.00	1.00	
Contractor cost	(£)	345.57	345.57	345.57	
Cost of labour	(£ h ⁻¹)	17.28	17.28	17.28	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	631	238	238	369
Maintenance					
Administrative cost of forestry	(€ ha ⁻¹)	92.15	92.15	92.15	
Insurance management	(€ ha ⁻¹)	0	0	0	
Sub-total	(€ ha ⁻¹)	92	92	92	92

^(a) establishment hours are at around 500 for planting, 500 watering first year, including volunteer groups that were used for engagement purposes and were far more than a contractor would have needed to complete the work

^(b) wild flower strips should be maintained indefinitely under the trees

^(c) currently do not pay for maintenance machinery as it is done for free by a neighbour

^(d) had first prune in tree nursery; not pruned yet at farm

^(e) Unsure when final year is

^(f) first prune was so small that the prunings were left in wildflower strips

4 Discussion and conclusions: next steps for financial modelling

During 2024, we will work with stakeholders at each Living Lab to derive values for missing inputs and outputs and progress the financial modelling of the described agroforestry systems. There are a range of models that can be used to compare the benefits and costs of the agroforestry innovation relative to the baseline system. Because agroforestry systems exist over multiple years, a common feature of the financial modelling of tree-based systems is the need to account for preference for money in the present (Graves et al., 2011). Hence future benefits and costs can be given “net present values” using a discount factor to systematically reduce their current importance as the time that has elapsed since the start of the project increases. The present values of the costs and benefits over the defined time horizon are then aggregated into a single value known as the net present value (*NPV*; units: € ha⁻¹) where the revenue (R_t), variable costs (V_t), and assignable fixed costs (A_t) are specified for each year (t) over a time horizon of T (years) with i as the discount rate (Equation 3).

$$NPV = \sum_{t=0}^{t=T} \frac{(R_t - V_t - A_t)}{(1 + i)^t} \quad \text{Equation 3}$$

4.1 Examples of digital models to support financial analysis

In 2005, Graves et al. (2005) reviewed the availability of digital models to support the financial analysis of agroforestry systems. At that time, the models available included POPMOD, ARBUSTRA, the Agroforestry Estate Model, WaNuLCAS, and the Agroforestry Calculator. Although there are recent reports on WaNuLCas (van Noordwijk et al. 2011), it can be difficult to operate on current computer software. Elements of ARBUSTRA and POPMOD were used in the development of the Farm-SAFE model described below. Three potential bioeconomic models to compare agroforestry systems with a baseline system are described below.

4.1.1 Farm-SAFE

The original Farm-SAFE model was developed in 2006 as part of the European Union sponsored SAFE project (2001-2005) (Graves et al., 2011). The Microsoft Excel model was developed to compare the financial aspects of arable, forestry and agroforestry systems using discounted cash flow analysis for up to 60 years. It is able to model arable, forestry, and silvoarable systems across four areas of a farm or region to determine the feasibility and implications of introducing agroforestry across four areas of a farm or region to determine the feasibility and implications of agroforestry systems on European farms.

An updated version of Farm-SAFE called “Farm-SAFE_March17” was created during the AGFORWARD project (2014-2018) which links Farm-SAFE to an on-line version of the Yield-SAFE biophysical model (van der Werf et al., 2007; Burgess et al., 2023). Developments within the new model include the addition of new farm systems (e.g. short rotation coppice and fruit harvest), and an enhanced database of new systems (e.g. poplar short rotation coppice in Germany and cherry for fruit production in grassland in Switzerland, and organic silvoarable agroforestry with willow short rotation coppice in the UK). Farm-SAFE is available to be downloaded free of charge from the AGFORWARD’s website: <https://www.agforward.eu/web-application-of-yield-safe-and-farm-safe-models.html>.

4.1.2 AgroForstRechner

AgroForstRechner (or AgroForestry Calculator in English) is a user-friendly Microsoft Excel-based tool (Visual Basic for Applications) developed by DEFAP (Germany) that allows the comparison and evaluation of the economic viability of Short Rotation Coppice (SRC) agroforestry systems relative to the conventional cultivation of arable crops. It is different from the similarly named “Agroforestry Calculator” developed in Australia (Graves et al., 2005). The program includes a front interface for ease of use and operates using predefined or manually set input parameters, comparing and evaluating the management and economics of SRC agroforestry vs. conventional arable crops. Possible uses of the resulting woody material include: the production and sale of wood chips; the distribution of logs and the energy use of wood chips through Combined Heat and Power (CHP) systems. The Agro Forestry Calculator is available to be downloaded for free from DEFAP’s website: <https://agroforst-info.de/agroforstrechner/>.

4.1.3 INTeractive Agroforestry Cost-benefit Tool (INTACT)

The INTeractive Agroforestry Cost-benefit Tool (INTACT) has been developed by ILVO (Belgium) to guide the user through the relevant tree and shrub-related costs and benefits that can be expected while implementing agroforestry, including investment and maintenance costs, as well as expected income from trees and shrubs. The tool was developed for the context of Belgium and the Netherlands.

INTACT includes five categories of costs including 1) the purchase of trees and shrubs, 2) terrain and planting preparation costs, 3) tree protection costs, 4) tree management costs, and 5) harvesting costs after which these costs are summarized in a clear overview. Furthermore, INTACT provides both costs and labour hours per category of cost. Regarding benefits, INTACT shows the expected freshly harvested fruit and nut yield accordingly with the chosen trees and shrubs. Wood yield, based on the most recent timber prices, is displayed on a separate screen.

Potential income from derived products including fruit juices, nut oil, jam, or processed wood products are not included yet in INTACT 1.0. After navigating through both the cost and benefits modules, the final screen will show a cost-benefit analysis over 20 years based on the user’s input. As a result, INTACT can specifically offer a partial analysis focusing on the financial impact of a farmer’s agroforestry plan. However, it is important to stress that INTACT is not intended for an integrated business economic analysis nor for replacing guidance tailored to specific business situations. The first public version of INTACT was planned to be launched in January 2024, as part of the [Agroforestry Planner](#), an online toolkit consisting of several agroforestry decision support tools, created by partners of the Consortium Agroforestry Flanders.

4.2 Opportunities for further development

Computer simulation models are generally developed with specific objectives in mind. When selecting a model, it is important to consider what the developers intended it to be used for and what target systems it was developed to model. Farm-SAFE for example has generally been used as a research tool and was developed to simulate systems in a wide range of countries at a farm or region scale. This has made the “Farm-SAFE_March17” tool quite complex. Hence a simplified version of Farm-SAFE will be made available online in early 2024. The AgroForstrechner tool is designed for use by German farmers and advisors but it is limited to short rotation coppice systems. The Belgian INTACT tool is user-friendly and interactive, although it only considers the financial consequences of the tree and/or shrub components and not any other farm components.

During 2024 within work-package 2 of the DigitAF project, the planned roadmap is to work with each Living Lab to use and develop the existing economic models and the associated data to develop tools that are useful for practitioners. This process includes both 1) improving the estimates of the physical quantities of inputs and outputs, and the financial values of those inputs and outputs and grants and 2) improving the usability of the models. Among the potential approaches for improving the usability of models include a) simplifying the number of options; b) providing clear user guidance in the form of user manuals or short videos, and c) providing pre-populated databases so that users can learn from case study examples.

4.3 Conclusions

This report is part of an ongoing process to enhance the quantification of the financial benefits and costs of selected agroforestry practices relative to selected baseline enterprises, through the development, use and promotion of digital tools. An updated deliverable entitled “D2.4: Roadmap 2.0 on anticipated benefits and costs of agroforestry innovations” will be produced in August 2025. The intention is that the process of using and developing existing financial tools in the context of the living lab case studies will lead to enhanced tools for the financial analysis of agroforestry for practitioners.

The baseline systems and the agroforestry innovations being examined across the Living Labs are very varied. The baseline systems include arable systems, livestock enterprises, and mixed farms. On arable farms, the agroforestry interventions include alley-cropping systems with a) timber, fuelwood, or windbreaks (Italy, Finland, UK), b) fruit (Finland, UK), c) nuts (Finland, UK), and d) short rotation coppice (Germany). On livestock and mixed farms, the interventions also include agroforestry systems with a) timber/fuelwood (Czechia), b) fruit (Netherlands, Czechia), c) nuts (Netherlands), d) short rotation coppice (Germany), and e) fodder hedges (Netherlands). Incorporating these different systems into a single financial model is a challenge.

In addition to the above, the grant and subsidy systems for supporting or not supporting agroforestry can vary widely with country. Hence grants and subsidies can also be important in determining the benefits and costs at a particular site. Moreover for some stakeholders, the consideration of outputs that do not have a direct market value such as greenhouse gas emissions, carbon sequestration, soil conservation, and reduction of nutrient loss can also be important (Giannitsopoulos et al., 2020).

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Appendix A: Additional data for German agroforestry intervention

Table 25. Cost of purchase of trees for German case study

Species	Botanical name	Source	Number	Price tree ⁻¹	Total price	VAT	Postage	Total
Grey poplar (rooted)	<i>Populus canescens</i>	pflanzmich.de	200	0.99	185.05	12.95	0	198
Turkish hazel	<i>Corylus colurna</i>	fürst pückler	25	Gathered	0		Gathered	0
Black holunder	<i>Sambucus nigra</i>	fürst pückler	180	Gathered	0		Gathered	0
Serviceberry,	<i>Amelanchier lamarckii</i>	baumschule plieskendorf	180	1.1	198	13.86	Gathered	211.86
Turkish hazel	<i>Corylus colurna</i>	frondeus prima ungarn	100	0.23	23	6.21		29.21
Field maple	<i>Acer campestre</i>	frondeus prima ungarn	100	0.15	15	4.05	74.93	93.98
Common ossier / basket willow	dq18 <i>Salix viminalis</i> x <i>Salix daphnoides</i> (triploid, weiblich)	dendroquant	25	0.45	11.25	0		11.25
Common ossier / basket willow	dq20 <i>Salix viminalis</i> (triploid, female)	dendroquant	25	0.45	11.25	0		11.25
Common ossier / basket willow	dq22 <i>Salix viminalis</i> (diploid, femaleh)	dendroquant	25	0.45	11.25	0		11.25
Common ossier / basket willow	dq23 <i>Salix viminalis</i> (diploid, male)	dendroquant	25	0.45	11.25	0		11.25
Chestnut	<i>Castanea sativa</i>	philipp gerhard	50	30	1500	0		1500
Hybridepoplar max iii	<i>Populus canadensis</i> , <i>Populus euramericana</i>	lignovis	1350	0.3	405	28.35		433.35
Hybridepoplar bakan	<i>Populus canadensis</i> , <i>Populus euramericana</i>	lignovis	1550	0.3	465	32.55		497.85
Hybridepoplar fw ii	<i>Populus canadensis</i> , <i>Populus euramericana</i>	lignovis	525	0.3	157.5	11.03		168.53
Hybridepoplarl vesten	<i>Populus canadensis</i> , <i>Populus euramericana</i>	lignovis	260	0.3	78	5.46		83.46
Hybridepoplar marke	<i>Populus canadensis</i> , <i>Populus euramericana</i>	lignovis	1650	0.3	495	34.65		529.65
total			6270		3566.55	149.11	74.93	3790.89
bushes			460					
trees			5810					

Table 26. Yield data of SRC crops from German case study

Tree species	Plot	Row	Planting design	Rows (n)	Area (ha)	Area per row (ha)	Yield per row t FM	Yield per ha in tFM	Yield for harvested area	Average yield in t row ⁻¹	Average (t ha ⁻¹)			
Poplar	A102	9	2.7 x 1.0 m	5 rows	0.3375	0.07	2.86	42.37	9.06	1.81	26.84			
		8				0.07	1.94	28.74						
		7				0.07	1.58	23.41						
		6				0.07	1.12	16.59						
		5				0.07	1.56	23.11						
Robinia	A103	1	2.7 x 0.5 m	3 rows	0.2025	0.07	3.72	55.11	10	3.33	49.38			
		5				0.07	2.92	43.26						
		2				0.07	3.36	49.78						
Poplar	A104	5	2.7 x 0.5 m	3 rows	0.2025	0.07	5.58	82.67	15.22	5.07	75.16			
		4				0.07	4.38	64.89						
		3				0.07	5.26	77.93						
		2		2 rows	0.1736	0.17	18.92	109.01				18.92	9.46	109.01
		1		0.07										
Poplar	A105	10	2.7 x 0.5 m	5 rows	0.3375	0.07	6.6	97.77	29.08	5.82	86.16			
		9				0.07	5.62	83.26						
		8				0.07	6.32	93.63						
		7				0.07	4.32	64						
		6				0.07	6.22	92.15						
Total	4	18			12,536	0.54	82.28	82.28	1.32	152.37				

Table 27. Tree density of German case study (note there are rounding errors)

Plot	Number of trees	Area (ha)	Tree density (trees ha⁻¹)
A102	2340	0.68	3458
A103	2600	0.42	6173
A104	2600	0.42	6144
A105E	1300	0.39	3344
A105W	2600	0.39	6687
B106	1710	0.55	3112
B116	1620	0.51	3200
C108	522	0.23	2311
C109	1044	0.45	2313
D111, D112		0.15	
E101	2340	0.89	2641